

Internal Quality Assurance Mechanisms and Management of Universities in Niger State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed the Relationship between Internal Quality Assurance Mechanisms and Management of Universities in Niger State, Nigeria. The study was guided by two objectives with corresponding research questions and hypotheses. The research design used for the study was the correlational survey research design. The population of the study consisted of 1,560 academic staff obtained from all the three universities in Niger State. The sample size of the study consisted of 310 respondents. The instrument used for data collection was the 'Questionnaire on Internal Quality Assurance and Management of Universities' (QIQAAU). The instrument was duly validated and it yielded 0.75 as a logical validity index. The reliability coefficient of 0.77 was obtained after pilot testing the instrument. Descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions while Pearson's Product Moment Correlation was employed to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study indicated that there was a significant relationship between Carrying Capacity Policy and management of universities in Niger State and there was a significant relationship between staff recruitment policy and management of universities in Niger State. The study recommended that the laid down rules and regulations for admission of students into Nigerian Universities by the NUC and Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination should be strictly used by all universities in Niger State to avoid the high rate of students' admission so that staff will no longer be given much workload to enable them work diligently to enhance effective management of university system.

Keywords: Internal Quality Assurance, Management of Universities, Carrying Capacity and Staff recruitment Policy

Introduction

Achieving quality education at all levels of educational institutions in Nigeria is an issue of great concern to stakeholders in the Nigerian educational system such as the parents, community leaders, teachers, students and government. Quality education is useful and relevant to the needs, interests aspirations and values of every society. Quality education is an instrument for achieving sustainable national development. As a result, a series of control mechanisms are inevitable to position education for the development of human resources needed to lead Nigeria into an enviable position in the community of nations. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2014) ascertained that the major objective of the Nigerian educational system is to raise the quality of education at all levels so that the citizens can be trained to become more useful to themselves and the general society. Adams (2018) noted that education needs to be sustained and assured so that the educational system would continue to retain its quality of providing the citizens with the skills they need to survive and contribute towards national development.

The National Universities Commission (NUC) which is responsible for regulating the activities of Nigerian Universities in 2012 drafted a manual on University Quality Assurance and classified it into two categories to include internal and external quality assurance. Internal quality assurance is the policies and mechanisms designed by a university to achieve its goals and objectives. The NUC manual identified the internal quality assurance mechanisms to include the provision of physical resources, recruitment of quality staff, staff development, an annual evaluation of staff, employment of external examiners, internal supervision, provision of Students' Support Services, maintenance of Carrying Capacity, (admission policy), promotion of quality research, allocation of suitable workload to academic staff, effective continuous assessment, quality admission process and quality students' intake among others (Iyala, Muhammad & Sani, 2022). On the other hand, the external quality assurance mechanisms refer to the review by external agencies such as the National Quality Assurance Agency as well as the professional bodies that evaluate the operations and programmes of a university to ascertain the level

of compliance with set minimum standards. Examples of external quality assurance mechanisms include resource verification, accreditation, external auditing and collaboration with professional bodies. This study determined how the internal quality assurance mechanisms of Carrying Capacity and staff recruitment policy influence the management of universities in Niger State (Obadara & Alaka, 2017).

Management entails the organization and mobilization of human and material resources in a particular system to facilitate the attainment of the identified objectives of an institution. Management of universities in the views of Odigwe and Swem (2016) refers to the process that is designed to ensure the cooperation, participation, intervention and involvement of others to achieve the predetermined objectives of the university system. It involved the guidance, leadership and control of the efforts of a group of people towards the realization of common objectives. Akpakwu (2017) described the management of universities as a process that involves the executive function that executes the administrative policies laid down to achieve a high standard of teaching and learning in the university setting. The functions of quality assurance towards enhancing effective university management entail forecasting and planning, organizing and controlling, coordinating, directing, supervising, staffing, reporting and budgeting systems.

The demand for university education in Nigeria is increasing daily following the continuous increment in the population of the nation. Millions of Nigerians seek admission into Nigerian universities yearly which prompted the National Universities Commission (NUC, 2010) to introduce the Carrying Capacity System of admission after observing that many universities admit students more than their available resources. The Carrying Capacity System refers to the situation where students are admitted based on the available resources. The resources under consideration for admission of students into universities include the lecture rooms, quality of libraries, staff-student ratio, accommodation, and available funds among others. The essence of using the above measures for the admission of students is to enhance the effective coordination of activities in the university system. Okoroma (2018) submitted that admission policies

have positive contributions towards enhancing quality university education in the South-South Zone of Nigeria. Odigwe and Swem (2016) also concluded that there was a significant positive influence of the merit system of admission on the quality of education in universities in Cross River State, Nigeria. Ideally, universities that admit students more than the required numbers allocated to them are expected to be sanctioned by the NUC. However, observations indicated that in an attempt to meet up with their financial obligations, universities in Niger State seem to violate the NUC directives by admitting more students than the numbers allocated to them. Such violation which often leads to a high rate of students' enrolment may lead to over-utilization of available limited resources and such a situation cannot promote effective management programmes in universities. Okebukola (2018) observed that Nigerian university education was in a state of disequilibrium because it is difficult to match the rate of students' enrolment against available resources.

It seems the demand and quest for university education in Niger State continue to increase every year without the corresponding increment in the recruitment of academic staff. As a result, the few available academic staff members are overloaded with too much workload such as teaching, researching, marking scripts, supervising students' projects and so on. Such numerous tasks being performed by the academic staff could limit the quality of their job performance and their contribution towards the effective management of Universities. The greater workload allocated to the academic staff could also prevent them from conducting quality research for publication to facilitate their promotion. It also prevents them from working diligently towards effective management of the university system. Successful management of universities in the face of the limited number of staff may be very difficult to achieve (Urah, 2019). Obiekezie, Ejemot-Nwadiaro, Timothy and Essien (2017) conducted a study and found that lecturers perceived the availability of adequate and employment of qualified staff, students' attitudes to study, early publication of students' examination results, availability of well-equipped laboratories and workshops and funding of tertiary education as the most

important variables in academic quality assurance. The findings of the above study also agreed with Adeniyi (2019) who submitted that a significant relationship exists between the quality control mechanism of staff recruitment and management of Nigerian universities.

Enrolment into universities in Niger State is increasing at a high rate every year with stagnated human resources, thereby violating the Carrying Capacity Policy introduced by the NUC to ensure that every programme in a university admits students based on the available educational resources. On this basis, the available educational resources are overstretched and poorly managed. The assurance of quality in the university system in Niger State in the face of the above problem is an exercise in futility (Iyala & Sani, 2022). Hence, this study was designed to determine the relationship between internal quality assurance mechanisms and the management of universities in Niger State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

It appears there is ineffective management of universities in Niger State as a result of the mismatch between the academic staff and the continuous high rate of student enrolment in universities in the state. Such imbalance between the academic staff and students' admission reveals that universities do not adhere to the Carrying Capacity Policy which is meant to guide universities to admit students based on the available resources. The violation of the Carrying Capacity Principle implies that quality management of universities is difficult to achieve because of the over-utilization of the available resources. For instance, lecture rooms are normally congested during teaching and learning as the libraries in these universities are not expanded to accommodate the increasing number of students being admitted yearly. On this note, it is very difficult to achieve quality assurance in the process of university management.

Despite the indispensable roles which academic and non-academic staff members play towards the attainment and sustenance of academic standards in the university system, universities in Niger State are faced with the problem of understaffing, as a result, the few available staff are overburdened with too much responsibility that prevents them from contributing meaningfully towards effective management of the university system. This is because staff members with much workload cannot perform their job properly to facilitate effective school management that would bring about quality education. It is on the above basis that this study was structured to assess the relationship between internal quality assurance mechanisms and management of universities in Niger State.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between internal quality assurance mechanisms and the management of universities in Niger State. The specific objectives of the study were:

1. To determine the relationship between Carrying Capacity Policy and management of universities in Niger State.
2. To examine the relationship between staff recruitment policy and management of universities in Niger State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What is the relationship between Carrying Capacity Policy and management of universities in Niger State?
2. What is the relationship between staff recruitment policy and management of universities in Niger State?

Hypotheses

The study was guided by the following hypotheses:

HO₁. There is no significant relationship between Carrying Capacity Policy and management of universities in Niger State.

HO₂. There is no significant relationship between staff recruitment policy and management of universities in Niger State.

Research Methodology

The study was guided by the correlational survey research design. The population of the study consisted of 1,560 academic staff obtained from all three functional universities in Niger State at the time of conducting this study. The sample size of 310 respondents was selected using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) Table. However, the simple random sampling technique was employed to select the actual respondents from the various universities. The instrument used for data collection was tagged ‘Questionnaire on the Internal Quality Assurance Mechanisms and Management of Universities’ (QIQAIMU). The questionnaire consisted of 12 items and it was designed based on the modified 4-point Likert Scale given as: Strongly Agree (SA=4), Agree (A)=3, Disagree (D)=2, Strongly Disagree (SD)=1. The instrument was duly validated and it yielded 0.75 as the validity index while the reliability index of 0.77 was obtained after pilot testing the instrument that was computed using Cronbach Alpha. Three hundred and ten (310) copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents but eight (8) of them were rendered invalid by the respondents, as such, the remaining valid 302 copies of the questionnaire were used for data analysis of this study. The research questions were answered using the descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation, whereas, all the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Pearson product moment correlation.

Data Presentation and Analysis

Research Question One: What is the relationship between Carrying Capacity Policy and management of universities in Niger State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation Responses on the Relationship between Carrying Capacity Policy and Management of Universities in Niger State

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Mean \bar{X}	SD	Decision
1.	The university adheres to the Carrying	30	22	100	150	2.10	0.45	Disagreed

	Capacity System of admission which enhances effective control of students' behaviour.							
2.	School facilities are not over-utilized because students are admitted based on the available schools' facilities.	30	35	120	117	2.18	0.36	Disagreed
3.	There is poor management of staff because of too much workload is to them due to the high rate of student admission.	102	104	46	50	2.51	0.50	Agreed
4.	There is poor control of teaching and learning as a result of the overcrowding of students in lecture halls.	114	97	50	41	2.50	0.58	Agreed
5.	Students are properly controlled in the library because the rate of admission is not too high.	43	22	127	110	1.80	0.40	Disagreed
6.	Consideration is always given to the available resources in the University before students are admitted and this prevents overstretching of the school's resources.	15	35	151	102	2.04	0.55	Disagreed
Cluster Mean						2.18	0.47	

Scale Mean = 2.50

Table 1 indicated the relationship between Carrying Capacity Policy and management of universities in Niger State. The details of the table showed that item 1 had the mean value of 2.10 and standard deviation of 0.45, item 2 had the mean value of 2.18 and standard deviation of 0.36, item 3 had the mean value of 2.51 and standard deviation of 0.50, item 4 had the mean value of 2.10 and standard deviation of 0.40, item 5 had the mean value of 1.80 and standard deviation of 0.55 while item 6 had the mean value of 2.04 and standard deviation of 0.55. The analysis of research question one revealed that the cluster mean of 2.18 is below the scale mean of 2.50, this implies that there is low compliance of universities to Carrying Capacity Policy which prevent the effective management of universities in Niger State.

Research Question Two: What is the relationship between staff recruitment policy and management of universities in Niger State?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation Responses on the Relationship between Staff Recruitment Policy and Management of Universities in Niger State

S/N	ITEMS	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. Dev.	Decision
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		\bar{X}						
7.	The university has a proper plan on how to employ quality lecturers who are capable of undertaking quality teaching.	10	32	140	120	2.30	0.35	Disagreed
8	There is effective coordination of teaching and learning in the university because of clear guidelines for staff.	50	39	100	113	2.38	0.46	Disagreed
9.	There is poor job performance which leads to the disorganization of school activities because both the academic staff are not employed based on NUC guidelines.	54	35	103	110	2.15	0.55	Disagreed
10.	The university is not poorly controlled because the available staff members are not overloaded with a high rate of responsibilities.	30	44	138	90	2.40	0.40	Disagreed
11.	All staff members are qualified to perform the responsibilities assigned to them to enhance the proper organization of the programmes of the university.	28	31	108	135	2.23	0.48	Disagreed
12.	The problem of ethnicity makes the university not apply merit in employing staff to contribute towards effective coordination of the affairs of the University.	138	104	40	20	2.52	0.25	Agreed
Cluster Mean						2.33	0.41	

Scale Mean = 2.50

Table 2 showed the relationship between staff recruitment policy and management of universities in Niger State. The details of the table indicated that item 7 had the mean value of 2.30 and standard deviation of 0.35, item 8 had the mean value of 2.38 and standard deviation of 0.46, item 9 had the mean value of 2.15 and standard deviation of 0.55, item 10 had the mean value of 2.40 and standard deviation of 0.40, item 11 had the mean value of 2.23 and standard deviation of 0.48 while item 12 had the mean value of 2.52 and standard deviation of 0.25. The analysis of research question one revealed that the scale mean of 2.33 is below the scale mean of 2.50, this implies that there is a poor recruitment policy that hinders effective management of universities in Niger State.

Testing of Hypotheses

The two hypotheses were tested using Pearson’s product-moment correlation at 0.05 level of significance. The results are presented in tables three and four below:

Hypothesis One: There is no significant relationship between Carrying Capacity Policy and management of universities in Niger State.

Table 3: Correlation Coefficient Analysis Showing the Relationship between Carrying Capacity Policy and Management of Universities in Niger State

S/N	Variables	\bar{X}	Df	r-cal	r-tab	Level of Sig.	Decision
1.	Carrying Capacity Policy	2.10					
2.	Management of Universities	2.18	300	0.48	0.194	0.05	Rejected

Table 3 indicated the correlation coefficient of a significant relationship between Carrying Capacity Policy and management of universities in Niger State. The analysis of hypothesis one revealed that the r-calculated value is 0.48 while the r-table value is 0.194 at the significant level of 0.05 and 300 as the degree of freedom. Since the calculated value of 0.48 is above the table value of 0.194, the null hypothesis was rejected which means that there was a significant relationship between Carrying Capacity Policy and management of universities in Niger State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant relationship between staff recruitment policy and management of universities in Niger State.

Table 4: Correlation Coefficient Analysis Showing the Relationship between Staff Recruitment Policy and Management of Universities in Niger State

S/N	Variables	\bar{X}	Df	r-cal	r-tab	Level of Sig.	Decision
1.	Staff Recruitment Policy	2.20					
2.	Management of Universities	2.33	300	0.52	0.194	0.05	Rejected

Table 4 indicated the correlation coefficient of a significant relationship between staff recruitment policy and management of universities in Niger State. The analysis of hypothesis two showed that the r-calculated value is 0.52 while the r-table value is 0.194 at the significant level of 0.05 and 300 as the degree of freedom. Since the calculated value of 0.52 is greater than the table

value of 0.194, the null hypothesis was rejected which implies that there was a significant relationship between staff recruitment policy and management of universities in Niger State.

Summary of Findings

The following is the summary of the findings based on the research questions and statement of hypotheses:

1. The answer to research question one in Table 1 showed that there is low compliance of universities to Carrying Capacity Policy that is preventing effective management of universities in Niger State. The findings of hypothesis one in Table 3 showed that there was a significant relationship between Carrying Capacity Policy and management of universities in Niger State.
2. The answer to research question two in Table 2 indicated that there is a poor recruitment policy that hinders the effective management of universities in Niger State. The findings of hypothesis two in Table 4 showed that there was a significant relationship between staff recruitment policy and management of universities in Niger State.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of hypothesis one revealed that there is a significant relationship between Carrying Capacity Policy and management of universities in Niger State. The findings of the study agreed with Okoroma (2018) who concluded that admission policies have positive contributions towards enhancing quality university education in the South-South Zone of Nigeria. The findings of the study equally agreed with Odigwe and Swem (2016) who submitted that there was a significant positive influence of the merit system of admission on the quality of education in universities in Cross River State, Nigeria. The high level of demand for admission into universities in Nigeria keeps increasing due to the continuous increment in the population of people in the country. The introduction of Carrying Capacity Policy of admission by the National Universities Commission (NUC) was meant to ensure that universities do not admit students more than the available resources at their disposal. As indicated by the findings of this study, universities in Niger State admit students every year more than their available human and material resources

into their various programmes. The resources under consideration for admission of students into the university system consist of lecture rooms, library facilities, number of staff, accommodation, and available funds among others. Universities in Niger State in an attempt to meet up with their financial obligations and demands tend to violate the NUC directives by admitting more students than the available educational resources. Such violation which often leads to a high rate of student enrolment is responsible for the over-utilization of available limited resources that prevent the effective management of universities' programmes in Niger State.

The findings of the study further indicated that there is a significant relationship between staff recruitment policy and management of universities in Niger State. The findings of the study concurred with Obiekezie, Ejemot-Nwadiaro, Timothy and Essien (2017) who ascertained that lecturers perceived the availability of adequate and employment number of qualified staff, students' attitudes to study, early publication of students' examination results, availability of well-equipped laboratories and workshops and funding of tertiary education as the most important variables in academic quality assurance. The findings of the study also agreed with Adeniyi (2019) who concluded that a significant relationship exists between the quality control mechanism of staff recruitment and management of Nigerian universities. The quest for the attainment of quality university education remained a mirage without the provision of qualified staff members to perform their responsibilities with a high amount of commitment and dedication. Irrespective of the significant roles which both the academic and non-academic staff play towards enhancing the quality university system, the findings of this study demonstrated that many universities in Niger State have inadequate staff. As such, the few available staff members are overloaded with more responsibilities and such a situation influences poor job performance that leads to poor management of the university system. Due to inadequate staff, some university programmes have been de-accredited while some new academic programmes have been denied approval for commencement of academic activities. The effective management of every university depends on the ability of staff

members to effectively demonstrate teaching skills that will help students acquire the appropriate knowledge to enable them to function properly as members of society after graduation. However, quality job performance requires the recruitment of qualified staff to foster greater development and management of universities. The integration of the quality assurance index through the recruitment of appropriate staff would help to improve the proper coordination and planning of the activities of the university system.

Conclusion

The following conclusions were drawn based on the findings of the study:

The study concluded that the activities of universities in Niger State are not properly coordinated and organized because students are admitted more than the capacity and strength of the available human and material resources.

The study also concluded that staff members do not contribute meaningfully towards the effective management of universities because the recruitment exercises are not conducted based on merit using the NUC policies for recruitment into Nigerian universities as the issues of indigenization, ethnicity and 'godfatherism' have reduced the quality of staff being recruited by universities in Niger State.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of this study:

The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:

1. The study recommended that the laid down rules and regulations for admission of students into Nigerian Universities by the NUC and Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination should be strictly used by all universities in Niger State to avoid the high rate of students' admission so that staff will no longer be given much workload to enable them to work diligently to enhance effective management of university system.
2. The study also recommended that all universities in Niger State should organize workshops, conferences, seminars and symposia for all staff in the Human

Resource Department of their various universities to help them acquire the appropriate knowledge and skills needed for conducting proper human resource planning so that the right quality and quantity of staff could be recruited at the right time and place at the right position to undertake effective job performance needed for successful management of the university system.

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